

CLOSING THE LOOP: MIXED PET AND PLA WASTE TO BLENDS WITH IMPROVED RECYCLING POTENTIAL

Rebeka Lorber¹, Aleksandra Nešič², Silvester Bolka¹, Branka Pilić², Blaž Nardin¹

¹Faculty of Polymer Technology, Slovenj Gradec, Slovenia

²Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17301728

rebeka.lorber@ftpo.eu

Abstract: *Blending PLA with mixed PET/PLA waste offers a direct recycling route. Separating these plastics is hard due to similar uses. Even small PLA amounts degrade PET's thermal and mechanical properties, hindering its recycling. However, adding PET improves PLA. This study used PET as a benchmark and created three PLA/PET blends in varying ratios. These blends underwent 10 mechanical recycling cycles (injection molding and milling), with property checks after each. The blends maintained processability and most mechanical properties. In contrast, PET degraded significantly in toughness, strength, and processability after just 7 cycles.*

Keywords: PET, PLA, blends, mechanical recycling, mixed waste

1 INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand and consumption of polymers in a wide range of applications has led to an increase in plastic waste in recent years. To reduce the impact on the environment, it is necessary to manage waste efficiently, making closing the loop in circular economy even more important. The basic approach to the circular economy consists of the 5R rule: refuse, reduce, reuse, repurpose and recycle (Dorigato, 2021; Schyns and Shaver, 2021). Recycling can be divided into four categories: primary, secondary, tertiary, and quaternary recycling, where primary means mechanical recycling of pre-consumer waste, secondary means mechanical recycling of post-consumer waste, tertiary means chemical recycling, and quaternary means energy recovery. Mechanical recycling of pre-consumer waste is easy and very cost-effective because the source of the waste is known, while recycling of post-consumer waste is more challenging. The first and biggest challenge is the collection and proper separation of the material, on which the resulting material depends the most (Worrell and Reuter, 2014; Volfand, 2019). In terms of efficiency of separation methods, there is still much to be done, as many polymers are difficult and expensive to separate. For example, in the beverage industry, bottles as well as other similar products in packaging industry are mainly made from PET and more recently PLA as a bio-based and biodegradable alternative. Separation of these materials is challenging because the most common method based on density - the floating-sink test with water - is not efficient enough because the materials have similar densities (1.25 g/cm³ of PLA and about 1.35 g/cm³ of PET), which is higher than that of water (Harper, 2006; González-López *et al.*, 2019). PLA and PET can be separated by NIR spectroscopy, which is less economical and has been reported to result in 86 % - 99 % separation accuracy, which is hardly accurate enough for bottle-to-bottle recycling because PLA degrades at the temperatures required to process PET, resulting in yellowing and other defects in the recycled products (Gent *et al.*, 2009; La Mantia *et al.*, 2011; Alaerts, Augustinus and Van Acker, 2018; Gere and Czigany, 2020). The contamination of PET with PLA is a fairly well-researched topic, mainly revealing how much even small amounts of contamination negatively affect the rheological and

mechanical properties of the recycled material (Chen, Pyda and Cebe, 2009; Xia *et al.*, 2014; McLauchlin and Ghita, 2016; Topkanlo, Ahmadi and Taromi, 2018; Plavec *et al.*, 2020).

Considering the above and poor mechanical and thermal properties of recycled biomaterials compared to fossil-based polymers, this study addresses the challenge from the other side by exploring ways to improve the properties of recycled PLA, which include reactive reprocessing, the use of nanoparticles, and mixing PLA with other polymers (Hopmann, Schippers and Höfs, 2015; Badia and Amparo, 2016). Blending PET with PLA represents a simple way to treat post-consumer waste that is difficult to separate with an option to up-scale PLA in terms of mechanical and thermal behaviour, i.e., poor toughness, low impact strength, poor crystallisation behaviour, and especially thermal degradability of the recycled material. Since many studies have shown negative effects of mechanical recycling on PLA (Beltrán *et al.*, 2017; Schyns and Shaver, 2021), the prepared blends were mechanically recycled to evaluate their recycling prospects.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Ground PLA and PET pre-consumer bottles supplied by Stramex PET d.o.o. (Podplat, SLO) were used to make the blends. The ground material consisted of various particle shapes and sizes ranging from fine dust to 3 mm in diameter, with the average shifted towards the upper limit. Ground supplied materials were injection moulded and their properties evaluated. Determined properties are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Determined properties of base materials.

Property	rPLA	rPET
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	2.62 ± 0.23	3.53 ± 0.47
Tensile Strength (MPa)	68.20 ± 2.72	59.80 ± 0.48
Impact toughness (kJ/m ²)	15.34 ± 2.80	- (no break)
T _g (°C)	59.26	80.76
T _m (°C)	148.79	248.16
T _d (°C)	369.03	441.76
Storage modulus (GPa)	2.86	2.15
Tanδ peak (-)	1.942 at 66.96 °C	1.590 at 85.84 °C

2.2 Blend preparation and processing

The ground PLA and PET were dried in the Memmert 100-800 hot-air drying oven until the moisture content, determined with the Mettler Toledo HX204 moisture analyser, was below 0.025 % before mixing and compounding with the LabTech 20-44 co-rotating twin-screw extruder with a screw diameter of 20 mm and an L/D ratio of 44. Rotation speed was 800 rpm⁻¹, and temperatures increased from 165 °C at the hopper to 200 °C at the die. PLA/PET blends were produced in three different ratios: 95/5 (5 wt.% PET), 90/10 (10 wt.% PET), and 85/15 (15 wt.% PET) without any additives. The extruded filament was transferred through a water bath into the Scheer SGS 25-E4 pelletizer. The prepared granules were dried before injection moulding (Arburg Allrounder 320 C 500-100 Golden Edition with a screw diameter of 20 mm) into test specimens with the shape according to the standards ISO 527 (type 1BA), ISO 178 and ISO 179. The temperature profile was set to increase from 185 °C to 200 °C on the die, the screw rotated at 100 rpm⁻¹ at a backpressure of 30 bar, the injection speed was 50 mm/s, the holding pressure was set to 320 bar for 5 s, and the cooling was set to 25 °C for 20 s. Last forty samples from each series were analysed for their properties, while the rest were milled using the

Wanner C13.20 s mill for thermoplastics, and re-injected. Mechanical recycling, consisting of milling and injection moulding, was repeated 10 times.

2.3 Characterization

The thermal and mechanical properties of the specimens were evaluated after each processing cycle, however for more straight forward presentation the results of 1st, 3rd, 5th, 7th, and 10th cycles of reprocessing are presented. For thermal properties, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) were performed. Samples for DSC (DSC 2, Mettler Toledo) weighing between 5 mg and 10 mg were prepared in aluminium crucibles. The temperature regime of the analysis consisted of a 5 min isothermal section at 0 °C followed by heating from 0 °C to 280 °C at 10 °C/min, at 280 °C there was a 5 min isothermal section followed by cooling at 10 °C/min, in two cycles, and the entire measurement was performed in nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 mL/min. TGA analyses were performed using a Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC 3+. Samples of approximately 10 mg prepared in an alumina crucible were heated from 40 °C to 600 °C in a nitrogen atmosphere with a gas flow of 20 mL/min, followed by heating from 600 °C to 700 °C at 10 °C/min in an oxygen atmosphere (20 mL/min). Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was performed using a Perkin Elmer DMA 8000 dynamic mechanical analyser in dual cantilever mode. Samples were heated at 2 °C/min from room temperature to 170 °C in an air atmosphere and dynamically loaded at a frequency of 1 Hz and an amplitude of 20 µm.

Mechanical evaluation included tensile, flexural, and impact tests on notched specimens using the Charpy method. Tensile and flexural properties were determined using the Shimadzu AG-X plus universal testing machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell and an optical strain gauge. The tensile test was performed according to ISO 527-1 and the flexural test according to ISO 178. Impact strength was tested according to ISO 179 standard using Dongguan Liyi LY-JJD5 impact strength tester. Notched specimens were tested using a 1 J pendulum. The results of tensile and flexural tests represent the average of 5 specimen measurements each, while 10 specimens were submitted to impact toughness testing.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thermal properties

Figure 1 shows the DSC thermograms for the second heating cycle of prepared blends. The glass transition of PLA was recorded at about 58 °C, followed by its cold crystallisation in the range of 125 °C ± 5 °C and melting at 147.5 °C ± 2 °C for all samples studied, while the melting of PET was recorded in the range between 243.5 °C and 247.9 °C. No significant differences were detected between the tested blends by DSC, even between the 1st and the last recycling series of each blend. Due to the inhomogeneity of the samples taken out of injection moulded specimen, it was not possible to determine the effect of blend composition or recycling on the degree of crystallinity.

Figure 1. DSC thermographs of second heating recorded for blends

Similarly, the samples for TGA with comparable compositions could not be taken from injection moulded samples because the PET particles in PLA were not uniformly distributed. However, the degradation temperatures for the first decomposition (PLA) could be determined for all samples. The highest and lowest degradation temperatures were measured for the blend with 5 % PET after the 1st and 10th injection moulding of the blends, and the degradation temperature dropped from 368.6 °C to 360.4 °C. All other degradation temperatures of the other blends were in between. The content of PET does not seem to affect the degradation temperature uniformly across the different processing cycles, while overall consideration of the degradation temperatures seems to point to slightly decreasing trend from the 1st to the 10th recycling cycle, as shown in Figure 2. The general expectation was that the trend would be significantly decreasing, however due to better compatibility of the PLA and PET chains, which have shortened due to degradation resulting from multiple processing the decrease is probably suppressed (Worrell and Reuter, 2014).

Figure 2. Degradation temperatures determined by TGA

Considering the glass transition temperature (T_g), which is determined as the maximum of the loss factor measured by DMA, presented in Figure 3 (left), rPET has higher temperature of the transition compared to blends due to main material of the sample having higher T_g , however over multiple reprocessing cycles the temperature decreases while with blends increasing trends are observed, presumably due to the shortening of the PET backbone by the induced thermal and shear degradation and the resulting improved interactions with PLA. Furthermore, higher PET content in the blend seems to increase the retention of mechanical properties up to higher temperatures, as blends with 10 % and 15 % PET show higher T_g than blends with 5 % PET. Right side of Figure 3 presents loss factor values at peak temperatures. Loss factor of rPET over multiple reprocessing cycles decreases to less than a third of initial value, indicating stiffer and less damping behaviour. Blends are in terms of loss factor comparable after initial processing, however with reprocessing their dampening behaviour and suppleness are even increasing indicating the interactions between the components.

Figure 3. Glass transitions (left) and loss factor values at peak (right) determined by DMA

3.2 Mechanical properties

Tensile moduli of rPET and blends a function of cycles of mechanical recycling are shown in Figure 5. Moduli of rPET is in the similar range as 5 % PET blend, and it decreases with the increase of the amount of PET. After initial processing moduli of rPET decreases and stays in the range of standard deviation as long as it retains the processability. However, the multiple mechanical processing has no influence on the blends since most of the values obtained from the 1st to the 10th cycle stay in the range of standard deviation of each blend, yet again demonstrating the reprocessability of the blends.

Moreover, the tensile strength was not influenced by the PLA/PET ratio or by the multiple processing, but the tensile strength of PET from near 60 MPa at initial processing fell to almost 20 MPa after 7th reprocessing cycle. The determined tensile strengths are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 4. Tensile moduli (left) and strengths (right)

Figure 5 shows the results of the notched impact strength tests. PET loses significant proportion of its original impact strength each two cycles, while interestingly with blends no significant differences could be identified in dependence of PET content as well as loss of strength from initial up to 10th reprocessing cycle.

Figure 5. Notched Charpy impact toughness

4 CONCLUSIONS

European Union directives, such as 94/62/EC, in the field of packaging materials have become stricter in recent years, as have the expectations of society, which seeks a more environmentally friendly use of resources and a circular economy (The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, 1994). One of these strategies is the use of more environmentally friendly alternatives, bio-based and biodegradable polymers such as PLA, wherever possible. However, there are some disadvantages compared to petroleum-based polymers, such as lower performance and contamination of waste streams. Paper investigated potential solutions and recycling prospects for hard-to-separate packaging waste. Three blends were made from ground bottles and mechanically recycled 10 times. The results of the thermal tests showed no significant effects of the composition of the blend or the different

processing cycles on the first and second order thermal transitions. While the trend of a slight decrease in the temperature of thermal degradation as a function of the number of recycling cycles was observed, the difference between maximum and minimum for the blend with the lowest PET content was below 3 %, indicating a positive influence of higher PET contents on thermal stability in blends. Similarly, the retention of mechanical properties at higher temperatures was observed when considering the glass transition temperature, as increasing trends were observed as a function of increasing processing cycles as well as increasing PET content. As far as mechanical properties are concerned, decreasing stiffness was observed only for tensile modulus as a function of PET content. Surprisingly, other mechanical properties such as tensile strength, flexural modulus, and strength as well as impact strength did not change significantly as a function of composition or recycling. From a structural point of view, this makes the blends a perfect material for multiple recycling. Moreover, thermal, and mechanical properties of blends are compared to neat rPLA and rPET on competitive level, making them suitable material for various applications, as well as reprocessing since they retained the processability at least 3 reprocessing cycles more than rPET. Overall, the investigated properties of blends did not change significantly even after 10 cycles of mechanical recycling, showing an enormous recycling potential, which could be further improved by using powdered PET particles to improve the homogeneity of the material, coupling agents to improve compatibility of materials, nucleating agents to tailor the morphology, antioxidants to prevent oxidative degradation and chain extenders to keep the length of polymer chains.

Acknowledgements: *We would like to kindly thank the company Stramex PET d.o.o. for providing the material for the study.*

5 REFERENCES

- Alaerts, L., Augustinus, M. and Van Acker, K. (2018) 'Impact of Bio-Based Plastics on Current Recycling of Plastics', *Sustainability*, 10(5). doi: 10.3390/su10051487.
- Badia, J. D. and Amparo, R. (2016) 'Mechanical recycling of polylactide, upgrading trends and combination of valorization techniques', *European Polymer Journal*, 84. doi: 10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2016.09.005.
- Beltrán, F. R. et al. (2017) 'Mechanical recycling of polylactide: improvement of the properties of the recycled material', *Polymers, Characterization and Applications Research Group*.
- Chen, H., Pyda, M. and Cebe, P. (2009) 'Non-isothermal crystallization of PET/PLA blends', *Thermochimica Acta*, 492(1–2), pp. 61–66. doi: 10.1016/j.tca.2009.04.023.
- Dorigato, A. (2021) 'Recycling of polymer blends', *Advanced Industrial and Engineering Polymer Research*. Elsevier Ltd, 4(2), pp. 53–69. doi: 10.1016/j.aiepr.2021.02.005.
- Gent, M. R. et al. (2009) 'Recycling of plastic waste by density separation: Prospects for optimization', *Waste Management and Research*, 27(2), pp. 175 – 187. doi: 10.1177/0734242X08096950.
- Gere, D. and Czigany, T. (2020) 'Future trends of plastic bottle recycling: Compatibilization of PET and PLA', *Polymer Testing*. Elsevier Ltd, 81(July), p. 106160. doi: 10.1016/j.polymertesting.2019.106160.
- González-López, M. E. et al. (2019) 'Effect of Maleated PLA on the Properties of Rotomolded PLA-Agave Fiber Biocomposites', *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*. Springer US, 27(1), pp. 61–73. doi: 10.1007/s10924-018-1308-2.
- Harper, C. A. (2006) 'Handbook of plastics technologies', *IEEE Electrical Insulation Magazine*, p. 53. doi: 10.1109/MEI.2006.253437.

- Hopmann, C., Schippers, S. and Höfs, C. (2015) 'Influence of recycling of poly(lactic acid) on packaging relevant properties', *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 132(9). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.41532>.
- La Mantia, F. P. et al. (2011) 'Effect of small amounts of poly(lactic acid) on the recycling of poly(ethylene terephthalate) bottles', *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 97(1), pp. 21–24. doi: [10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2011.10.017](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2011.10.017).
- McLauchlin, A. R. and Ghita, O. R. (2016) 'Studies on the thermal and mechanical behavior of PLA-PET blends', *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 133(43), pp. 1–11. doi: [10.1002/app.44147](https://doi.org/10.1002/app.44147).
- Plavec, R. et al. (2020) 'Recycling possibilities of bioplastics based on PLA/PHB blends', *Polymer Testing*, 92(September). doi: [10.1016/j.polymertesting.2020.106880](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2020.106880).
- Schyns, Z. O. G. and Shaver, M. P. (2021) 'Mechanical Recycling of Packaging Plastics: A Review', *Macromolecular Rapid Communications*, 42(3), pp. 1–27. doi: [10.1002/marc.202000415](https://doi.org/10.1002/marc.202000415).
- The European Parliament and the Council of the European Union (1994) 'European Parliament and Council Directive 94/62/EC', (1990), pp. 38–59.
- Topkanlo, H. A., Ahmadi, Z. and Taromi, F. A. (2018) 'An in-depth study on crystallization kinetics of PET/PLA blends', *Iranian Polymer Journal (English Edition)*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 27(1), pp. 13–22. doi: [10.1007/s13726-017-0582-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13726-017-0582-5).
- Volfand, J. (ed.) (2019) *Razvoj embalaže v krožnem gospodarstvu: priročnik*. Fit media.
- Worrell, E. and Reuter, M. A. (2014) *Handbook of Recycling: State-of-the-art for Practitioners, Analysts, and Scientists*, *Handbook of Recycling: State-of-the-art for Practitioners, Analysts, and Scientists*. doi: [10.1016/C2011-0-07046-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/C2011-0-07046-1).
- Xia, X. L. et al. (2014) 'Degradation behaviors, thermostability and mechanical properties of poly(ethylene terephthalate)/polylactic acid blends', *Journal of Central South University*, 21(5), pp. 1725–1732. doi: [10.1007/s11771-014-2116-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11771-014-2116-z).